

Major agronomic characters of traditional and improved aromatic rices in Taiwan.^a

Variety or selection	Days to heading	Plant ht (m)	Grain yield (t/ha)	Yield components			Panicles		Awn	Grain size			Pericarp color	Lodging
				Panicles per plant	Grains per panicle	1000-grain wt (g)	Length (m)	Weight (g)		Length (cm)	Width (cm)	L/W		
Katupa-ai (Native) ^b	56	151	3.0	4.6	143	29.0	24.6	3.7	Long	0.78	0.37	2.11	Red	Severe
Chianung-yu 269 (japonica) ^c	64	100	5.3	11.3	131	24.2	18.3	3.1	None	0.69	0.33	2.09	White	Light
Chianung-se-yu 43 (indica) ^c	66	103	5.8	8.9	136	25.3	23.3	3.5	None	0.85	0.26	3.27	White	None

^aData collected in the second crop, 1984, at Hualien District Agricultural Improvement Station experimental farm at Chi-an, Hualien. ^bGlutinous. ^cImproved selection.

these rices offer vast genetic diversity for breeding programs. Unfortunately, the area planted to aromatic rices is decreasing because of low yields and the difficulty in processing caused by long

awns. Steps must be taken to save this valuable germplasm.

The traditional aromatic rices grown in Hualien probably are land races indigenous to Taiwan, although their

existence and production have not been documented. Their origin is unclear, but it is likely that early Ai-mei settlers brought the seeds with them when they migrated to Taiwan. ☞

Performance of three elite rice mutants

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BINA instituted a mutation breeding program in 1973 with local Nizersail to develop early-maturing semidwarfs with high yield potential. In the M₂, several mutants were isolated from the gamma irradiated progenies. Subsequent generations were evaluated and Mut NS1, Mut NS2, and Mut NS5 were selected in 1981. They were evaluated for various agronomic characters at three Bangladesh sites and compared

Characteristics of mutants derived from Nizersail, Mymensingh, Bangladesh.^a

Mutant, variety	Plant ht (cm)	Crop duration (cm)	Effective tillers/plant	Grains/panicle (g)	1000-grain wt	Grain yield (t/ha)
Mut NS1	148 a	145	10	184	18.2	5.2 d
Mut NS2	131 c	136	13	134	19.3	4.2 c
Mut NS5	91 e	136	12	110	20.1	5.3 ab
Nizersail	145 ab	155	13	118	18.5	4.3
BR4	115 d	148	10	153	21.7	5.5 a

^a Separation of means in a column at 5% level.

with Nizersail and BR4.

Varieties were planted at 20- × 15-cm spacing in a randomized block design with 3 replications. Plant height, crop duration, effective tillers per plant, grains per panicle, 1,000-grain weight, and yield were recorded (see table),

Mut NS1 and Mut NS2 were tall add Mut NS5 was semidwarf. All three matured earlier than Nizersail and BR4. Mut NS1 and Mut NS5 yielded significantly higher than Nizersail, but similar to BR4. Both seem promising for a rice - wheat sequence. ☞

Intensity and duration of dormancy in some rices

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Seed dormancy in rice is a desirable trait, particularly in prekharif and kharif (wet) seasons, for preventing losses to preharvest sprouting of seeds. If intensity and duration of dormancy are high, farmers who intend to use the seed for the succeeding rice crop have problems.

We studied intensity and duration of dormancy of seeds of 12 photoperiod-sensitive tall indica rices collected from

Intensity and duration of dormancy of 12 photoperiod-sensitive rice cultivars, Chinsurah, India.

Group	Cultivar	Germination (%)		Dormancy	
		Control (30°C)	Treated (50°C)	Intensity ^a	Duration (wk)
Weak, short-duration dormancy	NC1281	19	94	Weak (2)	8
	Seetasail	30	97	Weak (2)	9
	OC1393	7	96	Weak (3)	10
Weak, long-duration dormancy	NC324	5	85	Weak (4)	16
	Badsabhog	10	83	Weak (4)	16
	Rupsail	23	88	Weak (3)	16
	Kalma 222	6	80	Weak (4)	15
Moderate, long-duration dormancy	Randhunipagal	1	78	Moderate (6)	16
	Kataribhog	13	77	Moderate (5)	16
	NC678	5	77	Moderate (5)	18
	Kumargore	2	76	Moderate (10)	14
	Patnai 23	12	73	Moderate (5)	18

^a Figures in parentheses indicate number of days required to attain 80% germination following 50°C heat treatment.

fully mature panicles at harvest and subjected to 50°C heat treatment. The intensity of dormancy was determined by length of time required to break dormancy by heat treatment, and duration was determined by the time required to attain 80% germination at 30° C (control).

Wide variability in germination among control and heat-treated seeds

was observed (see table). Test varieties fell into three distinct groups: weak, short-duration dormancy (NC1281, Seetasail, and OC1393); weak, long-duration dormancy (NC324, Badsabhog, Rupsail, and Kalma 222); and moderate, long-duration dormancy (Randhunipagal, Kataribhog, NC678, Kumargore, and Patnai 23). Kumargore might be considered a fourth type

because it has strong, long-duration dormancy.

Rices with weak, short-duration dormancy may be used as donors for incorporating seed dormancy in cultivars to be developed for areas where preharvest germination is a problem and seeds are needed for the succeeding rice crop. *ℳ*

Assessment of dormancy in some late-duration rices

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We assessed dormancy in some late-duration, high yielding varieties (HYVs) and indigenous improved varieties (IIVs) grown under medium low-lying situations in kharif where mature crops often lodge under water.

Seed samples were collected 30 d after flowering and sundried to 13-14% moisture content. Percent germination, dormancy period, and dormancy intensity were recorded. Percent dormancy was calculated based on thrice replicated germination tests (100 seeds in each petri plate) at weekly intervals in an incubator at 30°C. Dormancy period was calculated from harvest to 80% germination. Intensity was determined by exposing the seeds to 55° C temperature for 4 d, followed by germination testing. Intensity was classified as strongly dormant (when it could not be broken), moderately dormant (when 50% was broken), and weakly dormant (when dormancy broke completely) after the treatment.

Among the HYVs studied (Table 1) CN499-160-134, CN499-160-2-1, CN506-147-2-1, and CN506-147-14-2 were strongly dormant: they showed no trace of germination until 50 d or longer after harvest, and were dormant till 80 d. Dormancy broke only after 7 d at 55°C. CR292-7050, CR292-5258, and CR301-3066 were weakly dormant. Other cultures had dormancy ranging from 10 to 32 d.

Among the IIVs studied (Table 2), FR13A was completely dormant for

Table 1. Dormancy at harvest and after heat treatment, and intensity and period of dormancy of some HYVs, Chinsurah, India.

Culture	Dormancy				
	Immediately after harvest (%)	After heat treatment (%)	Intensity ^a	Period (d)	
				Complete	Up to 80% germination
CR292-7050	0	—	—	—	—
CN499-160-13-6	100	7	SD	50	80
CN499-160-2-1	100	5	SD	50	80
CN505-5-32-9	100	91	WD	30	55
CN506-147-14-2	100	0	SD	52	75
CR292-5258	0	—	—	—	—
CN506-147-2-1	100	2	SD	60	85
OR330-40-3	100	95	WD	10	25
OR117-215	100	57	MD	25	42
BIET821	100	62	MD	30	55
CR301-3066	0	—	—	—	—
BIET807	100	68	MD	32	55
PLA100	100	88	WD	20	45
CR221-1030	100	97	WD	10	30
BIET724	100	90	WD	20	50
OR143-7	100	100	WD	15	35

^aWD = weakly dormant, MD = moderately dormant, SD = strongly dormant.

Table 2. Dormancy at harvest and after heat treatment, and intensity and period of dormancy of some IIVs, Chinsurah, India.

Culture	Dormancy				
	Immediately after harvest (%)	After heat treatment (%)	Intensity ^a	Period (d)	
				Complete	Up to 80% germination
Janaki	100	90	WD	35	60
Tilakkachari	100	56	MD	35	57
Agnivan	100	88	WD	50	70
NC678	100	93	WD	30	42
Raghusal	100	61	MD	42	55
Rupsal	100	97	WD	30	40
OC1393	100	54	MD	35	60
Bhasamanik	100	60	MD	35	55
NC492	100	3	SD	45	75
FR43 B	100	49	MD	40	65
SR26 B	100	0	SD	52	65
FR13 A	100	0	SD	65	90

^aWD = weakly dormant, MD = moderately dormant, SD = strongly dormant.

65 d. Other test varieties had 30-52 d dormancy. FR13A, SR26B, and NC492

had strong dormancy. FR13A required 9 d at 55° C for dormancy to break. *ℳ*